

The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by benzyltriethylammonium chlorochromate

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Abstract : The oxidation of six aliphatic aldehydes by benzyltriethylammonium chlorochromate (BTEACC) in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding carboxylic acids. The reaction is first order each in BTEACC and the aldehyde. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde, MeCDO, exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.89$ at 298 K). The oxidation of acetaldehyde has been studied in 19 different organic solvents. The solvent effect has been analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The rate constants correlate well with Taft's σ^* values; reaction constants being negative. A mechanism involving transfer of hydride ion has been suggested.

Keywords : Kinetics and mechanism, aliphatic aldehydes, Taft's relation, Swain's relation.

In continuation of our earlier work¹, we report here the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of six aliphatic aldehydes by BTEACC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. The mechanistic aspects are discussed and suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and discussion

The rate and other experimental data obtained for all the aldehydes are similar and only representative data are reported in the tables.

Stoichiometry : The oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by BTEACC leads to the formation of corresponding carboxylic acids. The overall reaction may be written as :

BTEACC undergoes a two-electron change. This is in accord to the earlier observations with other halochromates² and also with BTEACC³.

The reactions were found to be first order in BTEACC. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the [Aldehyde] (Table 1). The addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1). Thus a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is not operative in this reaction. The oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of acetaldehyde by BTEACC at 298 K

10^3 [BTEACC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[MeCHO] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.10	0.00	4.91
1.00	0.20	0.00	9.73
1.00	0.40	0.00	19.4
1.00	0.60	0.00	29.2
1.00	0.80	0.00	38.9
1.00	1.00	0.00	48.6
2.00	0.40	0.00	20.6
4.00	0.40	0.00	18.8
6.00	0.40	0.00	19.2
8.00	0.40	0.00	20.1
1.00	0.10	0.10	5.79
1.00	0.10	0.20	6.71
1.00	0.10	0.40	8.42
1.00	0.10	0.60	9.91
1.00	0.10	0.80	11.8
1.00	0.10	1.00	13.7
1.00	0.20	0.00	9.78 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

2). The rate constants and activation parameters are also given in Table 2.

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by BTEACC

Subst.	$10^4 k_2 / (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	1.45	3.60	10.8	25.2	64.6 ± 0.7	-94 ± 2	92.6 ± 0.6
Me	22.5	48.6	101	218	54.5 ± 0.8	-106 ± 3	86.2 ± 0.6
Et	39.6	83.7	162	342	51.7 ± 0.9	-112 ± 3	84.9 ± 0.8
Pr	43.2	90.9	180	369	51.7 ± 0.6	-111 ± 2	84.7 ± 0.5
Pr ⁱ	65.7	135	261	540	50.6 ± 0.9	-112 ± 3	83.7 ± 0.7
ClCH ₂	0.063	0.18	0.54	1.41	76.8 ± 0.8	-78 ± 3	99.9 ± 0.7
MeCDO	3.52	8.25	18.3	41.7	60.0 ± 0.7	-103 ± 2	90.6 ± 0.6
k_H/k_D	6.39	5.89	5.52	5.23			

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 1). The hydrogen ion dependence has the following form $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. This indicates that rate increases with an increase in acidity of the medium. The values of a and b , for acetaldehyde, are $4.91 \pm 0.09 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $8.66 \pm 0.16 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9986$).

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows the two mechanistic pathways, one is acid-independent and the other is acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of BTEACC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile (2). Both BTEACC and BTEACCH⁺ are reactive species with the protonated form being more reactive.

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PCC⁴ and PFC⁵.

Solvent effect : The rate constants, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (3) of Kamlet *et al.*⁶.

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (3)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of (3), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β have been obtained. Here n

Table 3. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of acetaldehyde by BTEACC at 298 K

Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)	Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	13.8	Acetic acid	1.86
1,2-Dichloromethane	17.4	Cyclohexane	0.54
Dichloromethane	14.1	Toluene	4.27
DMSO	48.6	Acetophenone	20.0
Acetone	15.8	THF	7.94
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	23.4	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	4.97
Butanone	11.5	1,4-Dioxane	7.41
Nitrobenzene	17.8	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	4.17
Benzene	5.89	Carbon disulfide	2.19
Ethyl acetate	5.24		

is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter⁷. Kamlet's⁶ triparametric equation explains ca. 84% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion⁷ the correlation is not even satisfactory.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation⁸ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also as eq. (4).

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (4)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. ($A + B$) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (4), separately with A and B and with ($A + B$).

$$\log k_2 = 0.44 (\pm 0.03)A + 1.77 (\pm 0.03)B - 4.37 \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9967; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.06$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.19 (\pm 0.58)A - 3.16 \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0063; sd = 0.47; n = 19; \psi = 1.03$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.73 (\pm 0.08)B - 4.23 \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9634; sd = 0.09; n = 19; \psi = 0.19$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.33 \pm 0.17(A + B) - 4.33 \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7810; sd = 0.22; n = 19; \psi = 0.48$$

The rates of oxidation of acetaldehyde in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [cf. (5)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 96% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 78% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 78% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.4811$; $sd = 0.34$; $\psi = 0.74$).

Mechanism :

In aqueous solutions most aliphatic aldehydes exist predominantly in the hydrated form⁹ and in many oxidations, in aqueous solutions, it has been postulated that the hydrate is the reactive species. However, owing to the non-aqueous nature of the solvent in the present reaction, only the free carbonyl form can be the reactive species. The rates of the oxidation of six aldehydes show an excellent correlation with Taft's σ^* substituent constants¹⁰, the reaction constant being negative (Table 4). The negative polar reaction constant indicates an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. There is no kinetic evidence for the formation of an intermediate in the present reaction, however, its formation in small amounts can not be ruled out. The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.89$ at 298 K), indicates that the aldehydic C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. The large negative value of the polar reaction constant together with the substantial deuterium isotope effect indicates that the transition state approaches a carbocation in

character. Hence, transfer of a hydride ion from the aldehyde to the oxidant is suggested. The hydride ion transfer mechanism is also supported by major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents.

High values of activation indicate that in the rate determining step bond breaking is more important in transition state. Large negative entropy of activation supports a transition state formed from two independent molecules.

Experimental

Materials : BTEACC was prepared by the reported method¹¹. Solutions of formaldehyde were prepared by heating paraformaldehyde and passing its vapours in DMSO. The amount of HCHO in DMSO was determined by chromotropic acid method¹². Other aldehydes were commercial products and were used as such. *p*-Toluenesulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Deuteriated acetaldehyde (MeCDO) was obtained from Sigma Chemicals. Solvents were purified by their usual methods.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, acetaldehyde (4.4 g, 0.1 mol) and BTEACC (3.27 g, 0.01 mol) were dissolved in DMSO (100 ml) and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for *ca.* ≈ 24 h to ensure completion of the reaction. It was then rendered alkaline with NaOH, filtered and the amount of filtrate was reduced to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was acidified with perchloric acid and extracted with diethyl ether (5%, 50 ml). The ether extract was dried (MgSO_4) and treated with 10 ml of thionyl chloride. The solvent was allowed to evaporate. Dry methanol (7 ml) was added and the HCl formed was removed in a current of dry air. The residue was dissolved in diethyl ether (200 ml) and the ester content was determined colorimetrically as Fe^{III} hydroxymate by the procedure of Hall and Schaefer¹³. Several determinations indicated a 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The oxidation state of chromium in a completely reduced reaction mixture, determined by iodometric titrations was 3.90 ± 0.10 .

Table 4. Temperature dependence of the reaction constant

Temp./K	288	298	308	318
ρ^*	-2.43 ± 0.01	-2.32 ± 0.02	-2.17 ± 0.01	-2.08 ± 0.01
r^2	0.9999	0.9998	0.9999	0.9998
sd	0.001	0.002	0.007	0.006

Kinetic measurements : Pseudo-first-order conditions were attained by keeping an excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the [aldehyde] over [BTEACC]. The solvent was DMSO, unless mentioned otherwise. All reactions were carried out in flasks blackened from the outside to prevent any photochemical reactions. The reactions were carried out at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and were followed up to 80% of the extent of reaction, by monitoring the decrease in [BTEACC] at 370 nm. The pseudo-first-order rate constant, k_{obs} , was computed from the linear least-squares plot of \log [BTEACC] versus time. Duplicate runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was calculated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{aldehyde}]$.

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